

A Study of the Constitution of the Reduction Products of Chloral and Bromal Amides.

By B. H. YELBURGI AND T. S. WHEELER.

The reduction of the group $\text{CHOH}\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ was studied by Jocitsch and co workers (*J. Russ. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, 30, 920, 998) and Meldrum and Alimchandani (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 1).

Using zinc shavings and boiling alcohol the former authors found that the reaction proceeded thus :

Using zinc dust and glacial acetic acid the latter two authors concluded that the reduction gives $\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CHCl}_2$.

The present research involves a study of the action of bromine, dry hydrogen chloride and dry hydrogen bromide on the reduction products of chloral benzamide, chloral acetamide, chloral propionamide* and bromal benzamide. The results indicate that with these compounds the group $\text{CHOH}\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ or $\text{CHOH}\cdot\text{CBr}_3$ is reduced to $\text{CH}:\text{CCl}_2$ or $\text{CH}:\text{CBr}_2$ under the conditions employed by Meldrum and Alimchandani (*loc. cit.*)

Action of bromine.—By mixing molecular quantities of the reduction product of chloral benzamide (4.72 g.) and bromine (3.5 g.) and hydrolysing the resulting compound by shaking it with water, the presence of the double bond was confirmed by the yield which was 6.6 g. (theoretical for addition 6.9 g.) If substitution had occurred the theoretical yield would have been 3.45 g. since half the bromine is eliminated as hydrogen bromide. The mechanism is as follows.

* These three reduction products were first prepared in these laboratories by Meldrum and Bhojraj (*Proceedings of the Indian Science Congress*, 1926, p. 146) by the action of zinc and acetic acid on the parent compounds. EDITOR.

Action of HCl and HBr.—The action was tried on the above mentioned four reduction products in dry ethereal solution and the work confirms the unsaturated formula for them. The mechanism is explained as follows.

The presence of the OH group in (IV) was confirmed by a number of reactions.

The chloral benzamide derivative has been studied in details.

(i) By the action of phosphorus pentachloride on (IV) an unstable chloro compound was obtained which was found to be identical with the unstable compound obtained by the action of hydrogen chloride on (II). This compound, not being stable, was transformed into an anilino derivative. The mechanism is as follows.

(ii) The reactions of phosphorus pentabromide are similar to those of phosphorus pentachloride.

(iii) *Threefold action of acetic anhydride.*—IV, with acetic anhydride in the hot, in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid gives (II) and in cold it forms the acetyl derivative $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHCH}(\text{OAc})\cdot\text{CHCl}_2$; in the cold in presence of alkali, it gives the anhydro derivative

(iv) By the action of phosphorus pentoxide, (IV) gives (II).

(v) *Twofold action of benzoyl chloride.*—In the hot, in the presence of pyridine, IV gives V ; but in the cold, the benzoyl derivative is formed.

(vi) By the action of demethylsulphate, the methoxy derivative is formed.

The action of hydrogen chloride on the reduction products of chloral acetamide and chloral propionamide under similar conditions to the above, gave similar results. The yields are not good, ammonium chloride being also formed.

The action of hydrogen chloride or hydrogen bromide on β -dibromoethylene benzamide, prepared by reducing the acetyl derivative of bromal benzamide with zinc dust and glacial acetic acid, also yielded the expected results.

The presence of the OH group in the compound β -dibromo- α -hydroxyethyl benzamide was confirmed by preparing the acetyl, the anhydro and the methoxy derivatives by treating the compound with acetic anhydride and dimethylsulphate respectively.

With acetic anhydride in the cold, in presence of alkali the anhydro compound and the unsaturated compound are formed simultaneously.

The proof of the presence of the double bond in the reduction products is further confirmed by hydrogen analysis.

It should be noted that the present work refers to amides only and that the saturated formula may be true in other cases.

EXPERIMENTAL.

β -Dichloro- β -bromo- α -hydroxyethylbenzamide.—A dry chloroform solution of bromine (3.5 g.) was slowly added to chloroform solution of β -dichloroethylene benzamide (4.72 g.). Bromine was absorbed very quickly in the beginning. The resulting product was hydrolysed by shaking the mixture with water and then crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 128-130°, yield 6.6 g. (Theoretical 6.9 g.). ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{NBrCl}_2$ requires Halogen, 48.2. Found: Halogen, 48.0 per cent).

β -Dichloro- α -hydroxyethylbenzamide.—A dry ethereal solution of β -dichloroethylene benzamide (10 g.) was saturated with dry

HCl or dry HBr and kept under seal for a week. The viscous mass, obtained on evaporating ether, gave a crystalline solid on treatment with sodium carbonate solution, rhombic plates from chloroform and petroleum ether, m.p. 118-19°, yield 10 g. [Found: C, 46.4; H, 4.0; N, 6.0; Cl, 30.1; Mol. wt. (by Rast's camphor method) 238. $C_9H_9O_2NCl_2$ requires C, 46.2; H, 3.9; N, 6.0; Cl, 30.3 per cent; Mol. wt. 224].

β-Dichloro-α-chloroethylbenzamide.—The above compound (2 g.), was heated with phosphorus pentachloride (1.85 g.) and the product obtained after the removal of phosphorus oxychloride under reduced pressure was crystallised from dry ether as plates, m.p. 102-03°. The analytical results were unsatisfactory owing to the instability of the compound.

The identical compound was obtained after saturating the ethereal solution of *β*-dichloroethylene benzamide with dry HCl and keeping it sealed for a week, the ether was sucked off by means of a pump and the product was washed with ether three or four times and crystallised twice from dry ether in a vacuum desiccator, plates from dry ether, m.p. 102-03°, mixed m.p. with the product obtained using PCl_5 , 102-03°. (Found: Cl, 42.0; $C_9H_8ONCl_3$ requires Cl, 42.2 per cent).

β-Dichloro-α-anilinoethylbenzamide.—The above chloro compound was treated with aniline (1 mol.) in presence of dimethylaniline (2.5 mols.) at 0° and the resulting anilino compound which separated was crystallised from chloroform and petroleum ether as needles, m.p. 190-92°. (Found: Cl, 22.8; $C_{15}H_{14}ON_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 22.9 per cent).

β-Dichloro-α-bromoethylbenzamide.—*β*-Dichloro-*α*-hydroxyethyl benzamide (6 g.) and phosphorus pentabromide (11.1 g.) were heated and the resulting mixture was distilled at 155-220°/25 mm. This product was redistilled and collected at 158°/8 mm. ($C_9H_8ONBrCl_2$ requires Halogen, 50.3. Found: Halogen, 50.9 per cent).

This product was also obtained by passing dry HBr through the ethereal solution of *β*-dichloroethylene benzamide and distilling the mixture under reduced pressure. ($C_9H_8ONBrCl_2$ requires Halogen, 50.8. Found: Halogen, 51.0 per cent).

Action of Acetic Anhydride on β-Dichloro-α-hydroxyethylbenzamide.

(a) *β-Dichloroethylenebenzamide*. — *β*-Dichloro-*α*-hydroxyethyl benzamide (2 g.) was refluxed for 4 hours with acetic anhydride

(in excess) mixed with concentrated sulphuric acid. The resulting product was crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m.p. 68-9°. Mixed m.p. with identical sample shewed no depression.

(b) *β-Dichloro-α-acetylethylbenzamide*.—The reaction was carried out in the usual way at 0° (or in presence of pyridine in the cold) and the acetyl derivative after purification was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether as needles, m.p. 146—48°. (Found: Cl, 25·7. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3NCl_2$ requires Cl, 25·7 per cent).

(c) *The anhydro compound of β-dichloro-α-hydroxyethylbenzamide*.—*β-Dichloro-α-hydroxyethylbenzamide* (2 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (100 c. c. 2 %) at 0° and acetic anhydride (0·9 g.) was at once added to it. The mixture must remain alkaline. (cf. Chattaway, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2495). The resulting product was crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m.p. 189—90°. (Found: Cl, 31·3. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 31·5 per cent).

The same compound can be obtained by heating *β-dichloro-α-hydroxyethylbenzamide* between 90-100° for about 6 hours.

A benzene solution of *β-dichloro-α-hydroxyethylbenzamide* was mixed with phosphorus pentoxide and refluxed on the water-bath for about 7 hours. The resulting product was identified as *β-dichloro-ethylenebenzamide* by means of the mixed melting point.

Action of Benzoyl Chloride on β-Dichloro-α-hydroxyethylbenzamide.

(a) *Anhydro derivative*.—The reaction with benzoyl chloride was carried out in the usual way and the resulting product was found to be the anhydro derivative, m.p. 189-90°. (Found: Cl, 31·3. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 31·5 per cent).

(b) *β-Dichloro-α-benzoylethylbenzamide*.—2 G. of the substance were dissolved in pyridine at 0° and benzoyl chloride (1·5 g.) was slowly added. The mixture was well shaken and kept in the refrigerator for about 4 hours. Needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 131°. (Found: Cl, 20·8. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3NCl_2$ requires Cl, 21·0 per cent).

β-Dichloro-α-methoxyethylbenzamide.—*β-Dichloro-α-hydroxyethylbenzamide* (2 g.) was dissolved in 2 % sodium hydroxide solution at 0° and dimethyl sulphate (2 g.) was slowly added with shaking. The methyl ether was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether as needles, m.p. 99—100°. (Found: Cl, 28·4. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2NCl_2$ requires Cl, 28·6 per cent).

To confirm the presence of the double bond in β -dichloroethylene benzamide it was analysed for carbon and hydrogen. The results agree better with the unsaturated formula. (Found: C, 49.8; H, 3.3. $C_9H_7ONCl_2$ requires C, 50.0; H, 3.27 per cent. $C_9H_9ONCl_2$ requires C, 49.5; H, 4.2 per cent).

β -Dichloro- α -hydroxyethylacetamide.—The process is the same as that for the corresponding benzamide derivative but ammonium chloride separates on keeping the ethereal solution saturated with hydrogen chloride. It was filtered and the solid obtained from the filtrate after hydrolysis with sodium carbonate solution was crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether, rhombic plates, m. p. 118-19°. The yield was about 50% while with benzamide derivative it was about 93%. (Found: N, 8.1; Cl, 41.3. $C_4H_7O_2NCl_2$ requires, N, 8.1; Cl, 41.2 per cent).

To confirm the presence of the double bond in the reduction product of chloral acetamide it was analysed for carbon and hydrogen. (Found: C, 31.1; H, 3.3. $C_4H_5ONCl_2$ requires C, 31.1; H, 3.3 per cent. $C_4H_7ONCl_2$ requires C, 30.8; H, 4.5 per cent).

β -Dichloro- α -hydroxyethylpropionamide.—The process is the same as that for the corresponding acetamide derivative. Here also ammonium chloride separated. The resulting product was crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether, rhombic plates, m. p. 116°. (Found: N, 7.6; Cl, 38.0. $C_5H_9O_2NCl_2$ requires N, 7.5; Cl, 38.1 per cent).

In this case also, the reduction product of chloralpropionamide was analysed for carbon and hydrogen. (Found: C, 35.5; H, 4.3. $C_5H_7ONCl_2$ requires C, 35.7; H, 4.2 per cent. $C_5H_9ONCl_2$ requires C, 35.5; H, 5.3 per cent).

β -Dibromoethylene benzamide was prepared by reducing acetyl-bromal benzamide (20 g.) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (80 c.c.) with zinc dust (6 g.) which was added at intervals. The mixture was shaken for about 4 hours and then filtered. On diluting the filtrate the reduction product was obtained as long thin plates from dilute alcohol, m. p. 75°. (Found: Br, 52.6. $C_9H_7ONBr_2$ requires Br, 52.5 per cent).

To show that the substance is unsaturated, it was analysed for carbon and hydrogen. (Found: C, 35.3; H, 2.46. $C_9H_7ONBr_2$ requires C, 35.41; H, 2.31 per cent. $C_9H_9ONBr_2$ requires C, 35.18; H, 2.95 per cent).

β-Dibromo-α-hydroxyethylbenzamide.—The ethereal solution of *β*-dibromoethylenebenzamide (4.5 g.) was saturated with dry hydrogen chloride or dry hydrogen bromide and treated as before (*cf.* action of HCl on chloral benzamide derivative). The product was crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether as plates, m.p. 130°, yield 2.5 g. [Found: Br, 49.8; Mol. wt. (by Rast's camphor method) 329.6. $C_9H_9O_2NBr_2$ requires Br, 49.53 per cent. Mol. wt. 323].

Anhydro compound of β-dibromo-α-hydroxyethylbenzamide.—*β*-Dibromo-*α*-hydroxyethylbenzamide (2 g.) was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution at 0° and acetic anhydride (0.7 g.) was added to it and the mixture after being well shaken was left in the refrigerator for 1 hour and then filtered. The solid was crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m.p. 162°. (Found: Br, 51.1. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N_2Br_4$ requires Br, 51.0 per cent).

The filtrate on being left in the refrigerator for 2 days gave a product, m.p. 74°. This was identified as the original reduction product by the mixed melting point.

(b) *β-Dibromo-α-acetyethylbenzamide*.—By carrying out the reaction with acetic anhydride at 0° in the usual way, the acetyl derivative was obtained as needles from absolute alcohol, m.p. 138°. (Found: Br, 43.8. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3NBr_2$ requires Br, 43.8 per cent).

β-Dibromo-α-methoxyethylbenzamide. — *β*-Dibromo-*α*-hydroxyethylbenzamide (1.5 g.) was dissolved in a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide at 0° and dimethyl sulphate (4 g.) was slowly added to it with shaking. The methyl ether was extracted with ether and crystallised, m.p. 124-26°. (Found: Br, 47.4. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2NBr_2$ requires Br, 47.5 per cent).

